

Project title: Crisis management in Citizen Science during the COVID-19 pandemic

Most of the questions below pertain to how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the way you manage the citizen science project you are currently coordinating (sections B, C and D). A small section (section A) is dedicated to the organisational structure of your project.

A. Coordinating a citizen science project

1. Besides you, how many people are actively involved in running the project?
2. How decisions are made in your project?

B. Your perception and experience of the pandemic

1. What was your initial reaction to the pandemic?
2. Did you treat the pandemic as a threat or as an opportunity?
3. Do you think that the pandemic has highlighted certain aspects related to managing a citizen science project or even the future of citizen science?

C. Your actions during the pandemic

1. As a coordinator of a citizen science project, how did you handle the pandemic?
Did you take any particular actions?
2. Do you happen to know how citizen scientists responded to your actions?
3. Did the pandemic create any needs (e.g., for new personnel)?

D. Difficulties faced during the pandemic

1. Since the start of the pandemic, did you encounter any difficulties?
2. Was there a need to deviate from the usual way of doing things in your project?